

[View this email in your browser](#)

Dear subscribers,

At **EU4Advice**, we believe that meaningful change in short food supply chains begins with care: care for our farmers, for our advisors, for our communities, and for the local food systems that sustain us. This is why we enjoy and feel so proud of our fruitful ongoing collaboration with **CORENET**. Together, we are building an environment where we try to make advisors across Europe feel supported, connected, and empowered to guide the transition toward stronger, more resilient local food networks.

Our synergy with COREnet is growing naturally and with great harmony. Thanks to the dedication of all partners, we are building an advisory community where we want people to feel valued and supported, and where collaboration becomes a foundation for lasting and profound change.

One of the most important recent moments for EU4Advice were the General Assembly and Crossvisit held in Valencia in October. These gatherings offered us the space to reconnect, reflect, and refine our shared vision. Surrounded by trusted partners, we worked through challenges together, shared our progress openly, and strengthened the bonds that keep our network moving forward with confidence and care.

in the COREnet French Roadshow, as well as in the incredibly inspiring celebration of the 10th anniversary of the French Short Food Supply Chain Network (RMT Alimentation Locale) in Rennes. This event marked a decade of dedication to local food systems: ten years of advisors, farmers, and institutions supporting each other to grow healthier, more connected territories.

These shared moments are essential. They help us listen to advisors' real needs, understand their challenges, and let them know they are not alone. Through EU4Advice and COREnet, we want them to feel supported, uplifted, and part of something larger.

Together with COREnet, we will continue to build and maintain a strong European advisory community.

Patricia Mora

Project Coordinator, EU4Advice

EU4Advice and COREnet Events

Since May, **EU4Advice and COREnet have been present together** at a number of events, working side by side to share knowledge, listen to community needs and support ongoing efforts to strengthen sustainable food systems:

- [**COREnet French Roadshow and the 10th anniversary of the French Short Food Supply Chain Network**](#)
 - [COREnet and EU4Advice Showcased **Best Practices to Support Small Producers** at Romania's Producers' Gala](#)
 - [**SFS Innovation Platform Event** on the Future of Knowledge Sharing Platforms in Europe](#)
 - [**AF4EU Final Conference** to Advance Agroforestry and SFSC Advisory Services](#)
 - [**5th General Assembly of the AKIS Coordination Bodies in Helsinki**, organized by the modernAKIS](#)
-

EU4Advice News

EU4Advice General Assembly in Valencia: Three Days of Collaboration, Innovation, and Learning

From October 14th to 17th, 2025, the **EU4Advice consortium gathered in Valencia**, Spain, for its General Assembly Meeting, hosted by Fundación Entretantos. The meeting combined field visits, strategic planning sessions, and collaborative workshops, strengthening the network's mission to enhance advisory systems and innovation in European agriculture.

[Read the article](#)

Events

EU4Advice took part in events to advance Sustainable Food Systems and Advisor Networks

In recent months, EU4Advice has taken part in a wide range of events across Europe, deepening its commitment to strengthening the network of short food supply chain advisors. Through gatherings focused on local food resilience, gender inclusion, peer learning, innovation tools, and community-led food system transformation, the project has continued to engage directly with practitioners, researchers, students and grassroots organisations.

[Check the past and future events here](#)

Publications

Check our Knowledge Hub

We are pleased to share a **selection of recent publications** that deepen understanding of short food supply chains, sustainable food systems, and the tools and frameworks needed to support their transformation across Europe. Together, these works explore the evolution of alternative food networks, the critical role of infrastructure in enabling short supply chains, the future of advisory services, the potential of digital innovation in food governance, and practical methodologies such as Urban Living Labs and logistics optimisation.

From reflective academic analyses to practitioner-focused handbooks and student-led research, these publications contribute valuable insights for researchers, advisors, policymakers and all those working to strengthen local, fair and resilient food systems. Each resource is available for download for those wishing to engage more deeply with the evidence and ideas shaping the future of sustainable food systems.

[Knowledge Hub](#)

An interview with...

Lukas Lagerweij

Gert Kögeler

Jesper
ZeihlundOlga
Grönvall
Lund

As part of the **#AdvisorsCampaign**, EU4Advice has carried out a series of interviews with advisors working across different parts of the short food supply chain landscape. The aim of this initiative is to highlight the essential role advisors play, shed light on their diverse professional profiles, and give visibility to the knowledge, experience and commitment they bring to their daily work. Through these conversations, we seek to show **the human side of advisory services**, illustrate the variety of expertise involved, and create a better understanding of how advisors support farmers, communities and local food systems. These interviews offer an authentic glimpse into their motivations, challenges and contributions, helping strengthen recognition of advisory work within the broader sustainable food systems transition.

- **Lukas Lagerweij** (Pantry)
- **Gert Kögeler** (Boeregoed)
- **Jesper Zeihlund** (Association for Local Foods in Denmark)
- **Olga Grönvall Lund** (Reformaten)

Do you want to join the network?

Articles

- [From Policy to Practice: Building the EU Market for Nature Credits](#)
- [Empowering Local Food Futures: Towards Resilient and Sustainable Food](#)
- [From Vulnerability to Resilience: Short Food Supply Chains in the Face of Global Shocks](#)
- [Horticulture, short food supply chains and area-based collaboration](#)

COREnet Latest News

COREnet Roadshow in Rennes

part in the 10th anniversary of RMT Alimentation Locale and to run the project's European Roadshow alongside the main event programme.

[Read the article](#)

#COREnetStories

The COREnet Stories series presents a collection of interviews conducted within the COREnet project to highlight the people, experiences and practices shaping short food supply chains across Europe.

Zoltan Dezsény

MagosVölgy ecological farm. Guided by sustainability, this small ethical enterprise feeds 160 households, while investing in soil preservation and bridging rural and urban communities.

[Watch it](#)

Katalin Kujáni

COREnet meets **Katalin Kujáni, President of Hungarian National Association of small scale farmers**. She highlights the need to support Hungarian small-scale farmers because they struggle to find innovative markets easily. For this reason, it is essential to create opportunities and share knowledge on how to do improve this area.

[Watch it](#)

Zsuzsanna Varga

In this #COREnetStories interview, COREnet spoke with **Zsuzsanna Varga, Group Leader at the Hungarian Chamber of Agriculture**, about how farmers in Hungary are navigating today's fast-changing information landscape.

Watch it

TIBOR SZABÓ

In Hungary, **Tibor Szabó** coordinates the **Open Farm Network**, a short food supply chain model boosting local agriculture near the Austrian border.

Watch it

Watch more interviews here

SUSTAINABLE FOOD SYSTEM
INNOVATION PLATFORM

The SFS Innovation Platform is a space created to support everyone working toward healthier, fairer and more sustainable food systems across Europe. We welcome new members and project contributors who want to share knowledge, receive support and work together toward a common good.

The platform offers a supportive community of researchers, practitioners, advisors, businesses and EU-funded projects, where people can share experiences, learn from one another and find guidance when needed. Members have access to a broad collection of thoughtfully developed resources (scientific publications, practice abstracts, case studies, training materials, and practical

[Join the platform](#)

COREnet and EU4Advice are funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or REA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

You are receiving this email because you opted in via our website.

[Forward this email to a friend](#)

[Unsubscribe from this list](#) [Update your preferences](#)

